

EFFECTIVE INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854340>

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Abstract: Today, it is becoming more and more crucial to incorporate innovative technologies into the practice of teaching foreign languages. This article presents a summary of recent publications on innovative technologies. We can see very effective methods in teaching foreign language. The study's primary lines of inquiry were outlined, enabling inferences concerning the viability and efficiency of utilizing innovative technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages. A large growth in the number of publications on the mentioned subjects suggests that innovative technologies have a chance to be used in the classroom by a foreign audience.

Key words: innovation, technologies, methods, foreign language, teaching communicative languages, direct method, audio-lingual methods, silent way, suggestopedia, innovative education.

The fields of science and technology are advancing quickly in the modern world. Every area of progress is advancing. Particularly, there have been huge advancements and major breakthroughs in science. One of the key criteria of today's education is that each subject be taught to pupils utilizing innovative teaching methods.

Foreign language instruction must make use of innovative pedagogical tools, interactive media, and new communicative materials. According to the European Framework Recommendations (CEFR), new teaching strategies and standards for foreign languages have been developed in our nation. It has written textbooks for secondary school and technical college students. The classrooms are furnished with stands and modern information and communication technologies in compliance with these specifications. Additionally, there is a growing need for studying foreign languages day by day. Each of the four components of a foreign language—reading, writing, speaking, and Listening—is broken down into its own set of insights and abilities.

Learning English has increasingly become important for both an individual's and a nation's development. Innovative teaching techniques should be employed or developed to help students develop their communication skills while also making the learning process more engaging. Any student's ability to think creatively is crucial to the development of their lateral thinking skills when it comes to learning a language. It is important to design an engaging classroom environment for kids learning English in order to captivate them and motivate them to pick up the language both explicitly and intuitively.

The learning of second languages has demonstrated that learners of all ages possess natural linguistic knowledge in a developing pattern.

What does “innovative education” entail, and what qualities does it have? The term “innovation” is frequently defined as a pedagogical criterion and is typically simplified to the concepts of “innovation” and “novelty”. However, the actual translation of the Latin word innovation is “into the new,” not “new”. J. Botkin coined the term “innovative” at the turn of the 20th century, outlining the key components of the “didactic portrait” of this approach that aimed to cultivate students’ capacity for self-improvement, independent search for solutions, and collaborative activity in novel circumstances.

The direct method of teaching, which is sometimes called the natural method, and is often (but not exclusively) used in teaching foreign languages, refrains from using the learners’ native language and uses only the target language. It was established in England around 1900 and contrasts with the grammar–translation method and other traditional approaches, as well as with C.J. Dodson’s bilingual method.

The classical (sometimes referred to as conventional) approach of teaching Greek and Latin is where the grammar-translation technique of teaching foreign languages originated. Students study grammar principles in grammar translation classes and then put those rules into practice by translating phrases between the target language and their home tongue. It can be necessary for advanced pupils to translate entire texts word-by-word.

The approach seeks to advance students’ overall intellectual growth as well as their ability to read and translate works of literature published in the original language. It has its roots in the practice of teaching Latin; in the early 1500s, students learnt the language for conversation, but once it became extinct, it was only studied as a field of study. In the nineteenth century, when educators began instructing in other foreign languages.

The audio-lingual method, also known as the Army Method or New Key, is a method of teaching foreign languages that has been criticized for its shortcomings. It is based on behaviorist theory, which says that humans, in this case, can learn certain characteristics by using a system of reinforcement. Positive feedback would be given for using a trait correctly, while negative feedback would be given for using a trait incorrectly. The direct method, an earlier method of language learning, was similar to this one. Like the immediate technique, the sound lingual strategy exhorted that understudies ought to be instructed a language straightforwardly, without utilizing the understudies’ local language to make sense of new words or syntax in the objective language. However, in contrast to the direct approach, the audio-lingual approach did not place an emphasis on teaching vocabulary. Instead, the teacher taught the students how to use grammar.

The underlying methodology This strategy considers language to be a complex of syntactic rules which are to be educated each in turn in a set request. As an illustration, the present continuous tense, which uses “to be” as an auxiliary, is practiced prior to the verb “to be.”

The Bulgarian psychotherapist Georgi Lozanov developed the teaching strategy known as Suggestopedia. The majority of its use is for language instruction. When it was first developed in the 1970s, the theory used positive suggestion in the classroom. Be that as it may, as the strategy improved, it has zeroed in more on “desuggestive learning” and presently is frequently called “desuggestopedia”. Suggestopedia is a mashup of the words “pedagogy” and “suggestion.” It is a common misunderstanding to associate “hypnosis” with “suggestion.”

Teaching communicative language This approach aims to teach the student how to communicate in a manner that is appropriate and effective for the various situations she might encounter. Functions like inviting, suggesting, and complaining, as well as concepts like the expression of time, quantity, and location, make up the content of CLT courses.

The Way of Silence This is purported on the grounds that the point of the instructor is to say as close to nothing as conceivable all together that the student can be in charge of what he needs to say. Mother tongue is not used at all.

Local area Language Learning. In order to ensure that there are no impediments to learning, this approach makes an effort to establish personal connections between the teacher and the student. The teacher translates a lot of the conversation so that the student can repeat it in their mother tongue.

Due to an increase in the general technical level of support and the development of the methodology itself, which is constantly in search of the most effective, accessible methods, techniques, and teaching methods aimed at “achieving the maximum possible mutual understanding in a multipolar world,” the issue of using innovative technologies in the process of teaching foreign language (EFL) seems to be particularly relevant in recent decades [7]. Currently, the availability of competent speech (oral and written), the capacity to communicate effectively, and knowledge of speech influence and persuasion techniques are critical to a specialist’s competitiveness in today’s labor market. “A child enters the spiritual life of the people around him only through the medium of the native language,” asserts K.D. Ushinsky.

To sum up, Teaching foreign language in Uzbekistan has become very important since the first day of the Independence of our country, which pays much attention to rising of education level of people, their intellectual growth.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to English language development for the younger generation. Especially, in 21st century, the demand for English language has increased. Like many other subjects taught in school, the subject of the English language is one of the most relevant and demanded. The relevance of learning English is dictated by the needs of the modern world. Nowadays, the English language has

become an international language of communication. The President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev pays special attention to this sphere, which has an important place in ensuring the future of the country and its development

In today's process of globalization, the effect of the radical reform of the education system of Uzbekistan is evident in all areas related to this area. The state pays special attention to the teaching and further development of foreign languages in the education system. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on May 6, 2021 on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, the problems in the system were identified.

On this basis, the issue of attitudes to foreign language teaching is addressed in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 No PP-5117 "On measures to bring the promotion of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level": " education in foreign languages It is no coincidence that the need to develop as a policy priority, radically improve the quality of education in this area, attract qualified teachers to the field and increase the population's interest in learning foreign languages

In addition, English language has been recognized as a world language and now it is used by people all over the world. In Uzbekistan English language classes have been taught in schools since the first grade.

REFERENCES:

1. Otaboyeva M. P. Chet tilini o'qitishda zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalaridan Foydalanish va uning samaradorligi // Молодой ученый. — 2017. — №4.2. — С. 36-37. — URL <https://moluch.ru/archive/138/39058/> (дата обращения: 14.02.2020).
2. Zhou, G. & Niu, X. (2015). Approaches to language teaching and learning. Journal of Language Teaching and Research, 6(4), p. 798
3. Reimann, Andrew (January 2018). Behaviorist Learning Theory. The TESOL Encyclopedia of English Language Teaching. Pp. 1- Doi:10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0155. ISBN 9781118784228.
4. . Lozanov, Georgi. Suggestology and Suggestopedy. <http://lozanov.hit.bg/4/30/2006>
5. Utler Y.G. (2009). Teaching English to young learners: The influence of global and Local factors. In J. Enever, J. Moon, & U. Raman (Eds.), Young learner English language policy and implementation: International perspectives (pp. 23-29). Reading, UK: Garnet Education. P. 88-89.
6. Cameron L. (2003). Challenges for ELT from the expansion in teaching children. ELT Journal. 57 (2). P. 105-106.

7. Garton S., Copland F. & Burns A. (2011). Investigating global practices in teaching English to young learners. London, UK: British Council and Aston University. P. 136-139.
8. Resolution of the President of the Republic Of Uzbekistan No. PP-5117 of May 19, 2021 // [HTTPS://LEX.UZ/DOCS/5426736](https://lex.uz/docs/5426736)